

Kinematics dependent jet transport coefficient in cold nuclear matter

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The jet transport coefficient \hat{q} in a nuclear medium encodes the non-perturbative properties 'seen' by the jet traversing the medium, and the dependence of \hat{q} on kinematic variables is of fundamental importance. I briefly review our recent work on applying the global analysis to the extraction of the \hat{q} in cold nuclear matter within the framework of the high-twist factorization, which suggests that the \hat{q} may have a non-trivial kinematic dependence. I will discuss the connection between our results and the recent studies of \hat{q} in both cold nuclear matter and quark-gluon plasma. Future applications of our results to the study of nuclear-medium modifications in electron-ion collisions and in proton-nucleus collisions at RHIC and LHC are also discussed.

I. INTRODUCTION

When a jet produced in high-energy nuclear collisions encounters and traverses the nuclear medium environment, it can receive modifications which usually manifest themselves in forms of transverse momentum broadening, energy loss and changed substructures. Quantifying these modifications relative to the reference collision systems in absence of nuclear matter, such as proton-proton and electron-proton systems, can provide insight into the non-perturbative properties of the nuclear media (e.g. the partonic density). Related techniques are known as the jet tomography of nuclear matter [1, 2], which has been extensively developed in the study of jet quenching phenomena in relativistic heavy-ion collisions to disclose the properties of quark-gluon plasma (QGP).

Theoretically, the medium property reflected by the nuclear modification of a jet is encoded into the jet transport coefficient \hat{q} , defined as the transverse momentum broadening of the jet per unit propagation length in the medium, which is, however, not independent of other transport coefficients such as the specific shear viscosity of the medium [3]. In the past two decades, focus is on extracting the temperature dependence of the \hat{q}/T^3 from the jet quenching data, e.g., a well-known work was performed by JET Collaboration [4]. However, it is not an easy task to exactly extract this dependence. On one hand, the complicated (and coupled) evolutions of the collision system and the in-medium jet can introduce the theoretical uncertainties. On the other hand, the parametrization of the unknown temperature dependence may also limit the extracted result. For example, no obvious temperature dependence of \hat{q}/T^3 was observed from a

Bayesian analysis performed by the JETSCAPE Collaboration [5]. Recently, a significant improvement has been made by introducing the information field method to loosen the long-range correlations from the parametrization form [6], with which a non-trivial dependence on the QGP temperature is found.

Besides the temperature dependence, one can in principle reveal more detailed properties of the medium by extracting the dependence of \hat{q} on kinematic variables, such as the jet energy and virtuality. However, partly due to the difficulty of extracting \hat{q} in great detail, the possibly important kinematic dependence of \hat{q} has been sometimes neglected. Recently, more and more attentions have been paid on this topic, and some theoretical studies suggest that \hat{q} may increase with the jet energy [7–9]. Since the \hat{q} has the non-perturbative nature, one has to resort to the experimental data. In the Bayesian analysis mentioned above [5], the JETSCAPE Collaboration found no obvious jet energy (momentum) dependence of the \hat{q} in QGP, which is possibly limited by both the parametrization form of \hat{q} and the current experimental measurements.

Even though the kinematic dependence of the \hat{q} in QGP is far from well quantified, the physical origin of the kinematic dependence is of fundamental importance. An analogy may be the partonic structure of a nucleon (or nucleus) 'seen' by a probe, which depends on both the energy of the probe and the resolution scale. This kinematics dependent partonic structure is described by the parton distribution functions (PDFs), and can be extracted through a global analysis based on the factorization in perturbative QCD.

Alongside the study of \hat{q} in QGP, the study of \hat{q} in cold nuclear matter (CNM) is of particular interest. Compared with nucleus-nucleus collisions, proton-nucleus and electron-nucleus collisions provide a clean environment to make both the experimental and theoretical studies more controllable and reliable, thus allow a delicate study of

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FIG. 1: Schematic diagram of parton multiple scattering in DIS.

the kinematic dependence of the \hat{q} in CNM, which may in turn be instructive for the study of QGP. Furthermore, the future electro-ion colliders in both US and China [10, 11] will make the jet tomography in CNM a unique tool for exploring the partonic structures of the nuclei.

Figure 1 schematically shows a case of jet-CNM interactions in the electron deep-inelastic scattering off a nucleus. A typical nuclear modification that is most directly related to the \hat{q} is the transverse momentum broadening $\Delta\langle p_T^2 \rangle$ of the final-state hadrons observed in semi-inclusive measurements. Theoretically, the leading contribution to the broadening is from the double scattering processes [12], whose cross section can be factorized at the twist-4 level within the high-twist expansion approach developed by Qiu and Sterman three decades ago [13, 14]. In this framework, the non-perturbative property of the nucleus relevant to double scattering is included in the twist-4 quark-gluon correlation function $T_{qg}(x, Q^2)$, which can be further connected with the transport coefficient \hat{q} [15]. Therefore, by generalizing the QCD factorization, the high-twist expansion approach provides a basis for performing a global analysis to extract $T_{qg}(x, Q^2)$ or \hat{q} , similar as the standard method for the study of other non-perturbative functions like PDFs. In particular, the \hat{q} related to $T_{qg}(x, Q^2)$ is generally a function of the momentum fraction x of the nuclear parton and the resolution scale Q^2 , approximately expressed as [16]

$$\hat{q}(x, Q^2) \approx \frac{8\pi^2 \alpha_s}{9R_A} \frac{T_{qg}(x, 0, 0, Q^2)}{f_{q/A}(x, Q^2)}, \quad (1)$$

where R_A is the nuclear radius and $f_{q/A}$ is the parton distribution function of the nucleus. Thus, the kinematic dependence of \hat{q} is naturally taken into account in the high-twist framework.

FIG. 2: Extracted optimal values of $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$.

II. GLOBAL ANALYSIS OF WORLD DATA

In a previous work [16, 17], we have tried to perform a global analysis of the world data on various types of particle transverse momentum broadening $\Delta\langle p_T^2 \rangle$ from proton-nucleus and electron-nucleus collisions, to see whether a same theoretical framework, i.e., the high-twist factorization, can simultaneously describe the selected data (e.g. in SIDIS, Drell-Yan, and heavy-quarkonium production and in different kinematic regions). We found that it works well. Especially, we found that by including a kinematics dependent $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$ in the analysis, parameterized as

$$\hat{q}(x, Q^2) = \hat{q}_0 \alpha_s(Q^2) x^\alpha (1-x)^\beta [\ln(Q^2/Q_0^2)]^\gamma, \quad (2)$$

the minimum total χ^2 is significantly reduced relative to that without considering the kinematics dependence of \hat{q} , which suggests that $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$ has a non-trivial functional structure. Note that transverse momentum broadening $\Delta\langle p_T^2 \rangle$ is generally insensitive to other non-perturbative inputs such as PDFs [12, 18].

With the extracted optimal values of $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$, as shown in Fig. 2, the high-twist calculations provide an overall description of the selected data [16], particularly in small- and large- x regions where the calculations with a constant \hat{q} can not well describe the data. As is shown in Fig. 2, the $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$ is obviously enhanced in both small- and large- x regions, which may reflect an increasing gluon density or saturation scale in the small- x direction [19] and an enhanced power correction in large- x region [20, 21], respectively.

This result is to some extent consistent with the recent theoretical and experimental studies. In Ref. [22], F. Arleo and C.-J. Naïm extract the \hat{q} in CNM as a function of x within the BDMPs framework, from the broadening $\Delta\langle p_T^2 \rangle$ of Drell-Yan dilepton and heavy-quarkonium, which verifies an enhanced \hat{q} in small- x direction. Note that the \hat{q} in Ref. [22] is the transport coefficient of the

FIG. 3: Transverse momentum broadening $\Delta\langle p_T^2 \rangle$ in J/ψ production in backward [panel (a)] and forward [panel (b)] regions in pA collisions at the LHC as functions of N_{coll} (centrality). Solid curve represents results with $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$ from global analysis [16] and shaded area corresponds to uncertainties. Dashed line and dotted band represent results with constant \hat{q} with uncertainties. Circles are new ALICE data [24] that are not included in previous analysis of \hat{q} [16].

gluon jet, while that referred to in our work is for the quark jet. In Ref. [23], Y.-Y. Zhang and X.-N. Wang study the parton multiple scattering in dijet production at EIC, where a kinematics dependent $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$ proportional to the gluon saturation scale $Q_s^2(x, Q^2)$ is assumed, and $Q_s^2(x, Q^2)$ is calculated by integrating the gluon TMD distributions. Besides an enhancement observed in small- x region, a weak dependence on the scale Q^2 similar as our result can also be seen in Ref. [23]. After our work in Ref. [16], the ALICE Collaboration published a new measurement of the $\Delta\langle p_T^2 \rangle$ of J/Ψ production in proton-nucleus collisions [24]. By using the kinematics dependent $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$ and the constant \hat{q} extracted in our work, we compare both the two theoretical predictions to this set of data [25], as shown in Fig. 3. The data for the forward rapidity region, corresponding to the small- x region, definitely favor the prediction with the kinematics dependent $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$.

FIG. 4: $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$ at $Q^2 = 10 \text{ GeV}^2$ and uncertainties extracted from global analysis with and without ALICE data (2021) on transverse momentum broadening of J/ψ production.

FIG. 5: Extracted \hat{q} as a function of jet energy E_{jet} . Solid curve and shaded band represent optimal values and uncertainties, respectively.

Determining the uncertainties of the object function is an indispensable part of a complete global analysis, which makes the results predictive, testable and updatable in future studies. For $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$, the uncertainties are also important for confirming its kinematic dependence. The uncertainties of $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$ are kinematics dependent in general, since in different kinematic regions the constraining powers of the experimental data are different. Recently, we have applied the Hessian matrix method [26] widely used in the PDFs analysis to estimate the uncertainties of $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$ [25]. As an example, Fig. 4 shows a comparison for the $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$ with uncertainties extracted in the analyses including and excluding the new J/Ψ data from ALICE (as shown in Fig. 3). Obviously, the new data reduce the uncertainties of $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$ in small- x region, resulting in a more evident x dependence.

Since we have obtained a kinematics dependent $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$ in CNM, an interesting question may be that can we give its dependence on jet energy, and how to connect this knowledge to the study of \hat{q} in QGP? By noting that, in our analyzed processes, there is a common expression of the jet energy E_{jet} in the rest frame of nucleus, written with the variables x and Q^2 and the nucleon mass m , i.e. $E_{\text{jet}} = Q^2/(2m_x)$, we have converted the extracted $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$ into the form $\hat{q}(E_{\text{jet}}, Q^2)$ [25]. The converted results are shown in Fig. 5 as functions of E_{jet} . At a fixed resolution scale Q^2 , by increasing E_{jet} we actually reduce the value of x , while for a fixed value of E_{jet} , by increasing Q^2 we increase the value of x . Figure 5 demonstrates that, at smaller values of Q^2 (in smaller- x region), \hat{q} increases with the jet energy, whereas at larger values of Q^2 the jet energy dependence may be different. Therefore, the jet energy dependence of \hat{q} may be sensitive to the studied region of Q^2 , and if an experimental measurement integrates the contributions from a wide range of Q^2 , it may weaken the sensitivity to the jet energy dependence of \hat{q} . To extend this knowledge to the study of QGP will be of great interest.

FIG. 6: Transverse momentum broadening $\Delta\langle p_T^2 \rangle$ of single pion production in SIDIS as a function of Bjorken x_B at $Q^2 = 2$ and 10 GeV^2 , for three EIC facilities. Both theoretical predictions with $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$ and with a constant \hat{q} are shown for comparison. Circles with vertical bars represent estimated experimental uncertainties. Kinematic (x_B) ranges covered by three facilities are marked on top of each panel.

III. SUMMARY AND FUTURE APPLICATIONS

We have shown, within the high-twist factorization, the feasibility to extend the approach of the standard global QCD analysis to the extraction of the jet transport coefficient \hat{q} in CNM. In particular, we found a non-trivial but universal kinematic dependence of the \hat{q} from the current data on particle transverse momentum broadening in electron-nucleus and proton (pion)-nucleus collisions. However, the distribution of the available data in the $x - Q^2$ plane is very nonuniform, and most of them are concentrated in the intermediate- x (Q^2) region [16]. The experimental examinations in a wide kinematic region are imperative to consolidate the kinematic dependence of \hat{q} in CNM.

The future electron-ion collision (EIC) facilities proposed by US and China will be an important place for deepening our understanding of the kinematic dependence of \hat{q} in CNM. The nearly full kinematic coverage and high-precision measurements are the advantages of these EIC experiments. In a recent work [25], we have pre-studied the transverse momentum broadening in single particle and pairwise particles production in future EIC in both US and China. Figure 6 shows our theoretical predictions for the pion $\Delta\langle p_T^2 \rangle$ in SIDIS measurements in EIC. Both the results with kinematics dependent and independent \hat{q} are shown for comparison. The estimated experimental uncertainties are seen to be much smaller than the theoretical uncertainties from \hat{q} . The future EIC experiments are expected to provide a precise kinematic scan of the $\hat{q}(x, Q^2)$.

Besides the EIC experiments, the recent observations

of the enhanced hadron production in the backward rapidity region in proton-nucleus collisions at both RHIC and LHC provide a different insight into the kinematic dependence of \hat{q} . Even though the high-twist calculation that considers incoherent parton multiple scattering and a constant \hat{q} can well describe the PHENIX data [27], the same calculation did not reproduce the LHCb data [28], especially the rapidity dependence. Different from the $\Delta\langle p_T^2 \rangle$, the yields of the double-scattering produced hadrons are related to not only \hat{q} , but also its first- and second-order partial derivatives of x [29]. Therefore, the kinematic dependence of \hat{q} will affect the results in a special way. On the other hand, the backward hadron production may provide important constraints in the large- x region where the \hat{q} is poorly understood (as can be seen in Fig. 4). In a recent study [30], we have tried to study this nuclear effect and we hope to include this type of data into our global analysis in the near future.

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